

The Toponomastic Element **-land(a)* in Ancient Europe

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Introduction

Many place-names past and present in some areas of Europe show an element *-land*. This element is mostly found in modern France and the UK, but in ancient Northwest Europe generally, there are rare examples of this toponomastic element known from ancient sources. The best-known such example is Vindolanda, owing to the remarkable finds of documents there. The name is certain, as it is actually used in at least two documents.¹ It has always been interpreted as Celtic, with a meaning along the lines of ‘Whitefields’ or even ‘Brightfields’. Modern Insular Celtic, in particular Welsh, has been used to justify this, and indeed it seems quite convincing. But there is a problem with this interpretation.

Evidence vs. Lack of Evidence

There is a rather popular saying, supposedly a quote², which is: ‘Absence of evidence is not evidence of absence’. This, of course, is fallacious without further specification. First of all, if we state it in the positive form ‘Presence of evidence is evidence of presence’, we can see a tautology in that the ‘presence’ referred to could be that of the evidence itself³; in the context of toponyms, ancient or modern, the term ‘absence’ need not refer to ‘non-existence’, but rather is the opposite of ‘presence’.

The ‘presence’ in our context is the presence of a particular toponomastic element, in this case **-land(a)*. This element occurs mostly in some areas of Northwestern Europe⁴, being fairly frequent in areas that were dominated at some time by speakers of some Germanic language, in particular the formerly Roman province of Gaul, later France (the modern name being clear evidence of the one-time rulers, the Franks) and the formerly Roman province of Britannia, later Britain. The question is, to what language or language family does this element belong?

To answer this question requires a further specification as to time. Various languages have occupied the areas under consideration at different times, not least because language change has led to new languages (e.g. French over much of the area that at one time was occupied by speakers of a Celtic language, Gaulish). The toponomastic element in question exists - or is supposed to exist - as a lexematic element in at least two branches of the Indo-European family, one being Celtic, one being Germanic⁵. There can be no doubt as to its existence in the latter group. There is, however, some doubt about its existence in the former, which also brings into question the matter of borrowing.

A fairly widespread idea or hypothesis is that Germanic borrowed this element from Celtic. In view of several Celtic loanwords in Germanic, this cannot simply be put aside. But what if the element in question never existed in Celtic? That would mean three possibilities: either the toponyms containing the element cannot be Celtic, but must be Germanic; or said toponyms could be Celtic, but the element itself would still in origin have been Germanic, and so the toponyms would be mixed. The third possibility is that the toponym in question is neither Celtic nor Germanic. It could be Indo-European in nature, or not, but would then in any case be very early in date.

In view of the predominance in Northwestern Europe and the British Isles of clearly Indo-European toponyms in the late Iron Age and Roman periods, and that—as far as we can tell—the Indo-European in question in these same regions and during the same timespan appears to be Celtic, it seems fairly safe to disregard the third possibility for the time being.

1 T(ab.)V(indolandae) II pub. n°s 225 & 242 with complete examples; incomplete, but probable: 338 & 343. Cf. Fear 2011:66-7.

2 Allegedly said by Carl Sagan or Martin Rees, but actually older (one William Wright apparently wrote ‘Absence of evidence is not evidence’ in 1887 [<https://quoteinvestigator.com/2019/09/17/absence/>]).

3 Equally true of the positive form ‘Existence of evidence is evidence of existence’, although there is more to the matter in a philosophical sense.

4 It also occurs in other parts of Western Europe and its languages, notably on the Iberian peninsula and in Italian. On this, see below.

5 It would appear to possibly be present in Slavic also.

This leaves us with the first two possibilities. Toponyms with -landa would then have to be part of either mixed Celtic-Germanic names, or would have to be Germanic.⁶

This raises a further question. Assuming that Celtic (or part of Celtic) borrowed the toponomastic element *-land(a) from Germanic, when did that occur? There is no simple answer to all this.

The Celtic Etymology

There has been a certain tendency, particularly in Britain and France, to emphasise the Celtic past⁷, partly owing to the (principally political) desire to establish a long 'national tradition' or at least a long 'ethnic' occupation. This has naturally led to a degree of bias in examining place-names. Certainly there is such a Celtic past, and equally certainly there has not been anything like a complete replacement of populations in these countries at any time (a rare occurrence historically in any case), so there is, of course, some historical justification for the presumption of Celtic place-names. Notwithstanding, it seems simply to have been taken for granted hitherto that the element -land(a) must be Celtic in origin. Two examples may suffice here: O. Bloch and W. von Wartburg, in their *Dictionnaire étymologique de la langue française*,⁸ assume a 'Gaulois *landa, cf. breton lann « lande »', while W. Müller⁹ writes on the name *Üchtland* 'The only certainty appears to be that the second part of the word contains the Celtic landa "heathland, bush land", from which the French appellative *la lande* "the heath" is derived'. The French term does indeed mean primarily 'heath' or 'wasteland, uninhabited land'; but this does not necessarily confirm a Celtic (in this case Gaulish) origin.

In view of the rather severe limits on our knowledge of Celtic languages and peoples in antiquity, and in consideration of some of the exaggerated 'national' tendencies mentioned, something of a more sceptical eye should be cast on the evidence.¹⁰

One source of possible error is the reliance on insular Celtic languages for evidence of a lexematic (and toponomastic) element *-landa-. Although the element is apparently well attested in insular Celtic (Mod.W. *llan*, Middle W. *lland*, Cornish *lan*, Breton *lann*), it is noticeable that the attestations are all within the Brythonic branch; the element seems to be lacking in Goidelic. This could perhaps be an indication of the non-Celtic status of the element; if Goidelic represents an earlier Celtic immigration to Britain, Ireland and the other islands, and Brythonic represents a later immigration, or even if Goidelic represents an (early) immigration to Ireland alone, while Brythonic represents an (equally early) immigration to Britain alone, it is entirely possible that a Germanic loanword could have been present in the ancestor(s) of Brythonic and not in that (or those) of Goidelic¹¹.

6 The presence of mixed forms with a Latin element can be disregarded here, as no such are known that contain the element -landa.

7 The terms 'Celtic' and 'Germanic' are to be understood here as broadly linguistic in nature; the entire complex matter of what, who, and when goes beyond the scope of this paper. Cf. i.a. Lund 1998 and Mullen 2013 on various aspects of this problem.

8 3^e édition, 2^e tirage Paris 2009, page 360; originally published in 1932. Much the same is found in W. Meyer-Lübke, *Romanisches Etymologisches Wörterbuch*, Heidelberg 1992 (6th unaltered printing), page 397, lemma n° 4884: 'landa (gall.) „Heide“, „Fläche“, „Land“. It. landa, frz. lande, prov. landa, kat. llanda, asp. alav., pg. landa; westfrz. lād „Stechginster“. (It. = Italian, frz. = French, prov. = Provençal, kat. = Catalan, asp. = Old Spanish, alav. = Old Alavese Spanish [not to be mistaken for the Basque dialect of the same name!]. Heide = heath, Fläche = area of land, Stechginster = gorse.) None of these guarantees the Celtic etymology as such.

9 W. Müller, 'Siedlungsgeschichte und Ortsnamen in der Suisse romande', in: P. Ernst et al. (edd.), *Ortsnamen und Siedlungsgeschichte. Akten des Symposiums in Wien vom 28.-30. September 2000*. My translation; the original is as follows: 'Sicher erscheint nur, dass der zweite Teil des Wortes das keltische landa, Heideland, Buschland' enthält, aus dem auch das französische Appellativ la lande, die Heide' wurde.'

10 Not only toponyms may be affected: a word such as *leuga* has hitherto almost always been assumed to be of Celtic origin. This may be a sign of a latent tendency to believe the Celtic peoples to be somehow 'culturally superior' as compared to the contemporary Germanic peoples (probably with reference to the oppida of the La Tène period, but possibly also to the 'Fürstengräber' of the late Hallstatt). It seems to be based on perceived differences in technological ability (e.g. iron-working) and forms of settlement (the oppida appear to have been sometimes equivalent to towns). The aforementioned lexeme is, however, much more probably of West Germanic origin (cf. Simon, *Acta Antiqua* 2019); this would support (and be supported by) the thesis of the present paper.

11 A third variant is Celtic immigration to Britain and Ireland in several waves at different times; this indeed may be the most likely case. Shortly before the Romans came properly into contact with British peoples, there may have been a last wave of emigration from Gaul to Britain (possibly as a direct result of Roman pressure, perhaps compounded by pressure from Germanic groups).

But the element only seems to be lacking in Goidelic; apparently an Old Irish *lann* does exist. On closer inspection, however, this becomes suspect with regard to being an old, inherited element. In an important paper, L. Mac Mathúna¹² has shown that Irish *lann* may well be a loanword, resulting from British Celtic or even later Welsh contact; Pedersen 1913:3 only implies that *-lann* in OIr. *ithlann* ‘threshing floor’ is Celtic (and not a borrowing). There is thus at least a possibility that the element was not originally present in Goidelic. If so, and it was present in Brythonic, then it could still be an inherited lexical item in Celtic. But it could also be a loanword from elsewhere. The latter consideration could mean that it was borrowed at some time in continental Europe where Celtic and Germanic were in contact.

Naturally there is a fair degree of speculation involved; but that is true to an even greater degree of what appears to be the *communis opinio*, namely that the element **-landa* (vel sim.) and its continuants are to be seen as inherited within Celtic.¹³

It should also be noted that the Brythonic attestations all seem to have a similar meaning, namely ‘enclosed parcel of land’, later ‘church land, churchyard’, although in Breton the lexeme may also mean ‘heath(land)’.¹⁴ The preponderance of the one meaning may indicate that the semantic narrowing from the original range of meaning took place prior to the Brythonic migrations to Brittany, thus perhaps during the late Roman period. Unfortunately this does not indicate whether this is an inherited lexical item or a borrowing. Modern toponyms with this element do not have a general meaning ‘X-land, X territory’ or similar. Rather, such toponyms are, more often than not, connected very clearly to Christian themes, such as a church or chapel. An example is the Modern Welsh place-name *Llanfair*, which has the *llan-* element added to *-fair*, which is the expected mutation of the personal name *Mair* ‘Mary’. Another is Breton *Landouneq*, in French the place-name Saint-Domineuc.¹⁵

A source of etymological confusion with regard to place-names may be found in Celtic itself: a fairly common toponomastic element is *-lano-* or *-lāno-*, best known from the ancient name of Milan, *Mediolanum*. This particular toponym is widely attested in the ancient world.¹⁶ The derivation and meaning are uncertain¹⁷, but continuations of this element in French, for example, are indistinguishable from continuations of **-land-* when the latter is followed by a vowel, as assimilation to [-*n-*] is generally the case in such a phonetic environment. Toponomastic elements such as *-lanne(s)* could derive from either source, the decision as to which being dependent on the state of transmission of older forms, if available.¹⁸

Some points about the transition from Roman Gaul to Francia in Late Antiquity

Although the greatest Germanic influence on French is owed to the Franks, this linguistic evidence all refers to the area north of the Loire valley. There, we expect to find place-names with *-land(e)(s)* from early mediæval times.

South of the Loire there is also a number of such place-names. Here we may well be dealing not with Frankish, but with Gothic (specifically Visigothic) influence. The Gothic kingdom of Toulouse, after all, existed for nearly four centuries, and although Gothic was very probably the language of the elite ruling class only, this would have been time enough for toponomastic adaptations and changes to take place. Thus the Germanic element **land(a)* could well have been introduced throughout this region, too, just not by the Franks. In any case, it was not a question of replacement of names, but rather of modification.

A parallel situation may be seen north of the Loire; the introduction of Germanic place-name elements did not replace older names, but simply modified them. As to the area south of the Loire valley, since the geographical extent was more or less all of the later Bordelais, Aquitaine,

12 Liam Mac Mathúna, ‘Observations on Irish *Lann* “(Piece of) Land; (Church) Building” and Compounds’, in: *Ériu* XLVIII (1997), pp. 153-160.

13 Cf. Schrijver 2014:57, where this is assumed, but with the further assumption of another continuation of I.-E. **lend^h-* found in the place-name Londinium.

14 Cf. [https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lan_\(breton\)](https://fr.wikipedia.org/wiki/Lan_(breton)).

15 Hemon 1995:503.

16 Cf. Delamarre 2012:26-7.

17 Delamarre, loc.cit.

18 On the difficulties associated with odonyms, for example, see Gendron 2018:12-13 for some specifics, and the entire work for a clear and useful introduction to the study of odonyms in France. The caveats and cautions there mentioned all apply equally well to other toponyms and their study.

and a good part of Provence, any place-names containing this element could be from this period or later.

There is, in fact, little likelihood—and no evidence—that this element was taken over from the ancient Gaulish tribes of any part of Gaul. The presence of this lexeme (in various forms) in Iberian Romance and Italian probably represents a borrowing from the Romance of Gaul, rather than any direct borrowing from either Celtic or Germanic sources (see FN 4 above).

Romans, Celts, Toponyms

It is widely accepted, and there is good evidence for this, that the Romans tended to take over existing place-names, whether of settlements, rivers or any other, rather than replacing them. However, there were often modifications, usually in adapting suffixes to Latin, but sometimes consisting of additional elements in the toponym. Examples of Gaulish (or at least Celtic) suffix forms being modified include *Cambodunum*, *Lopodunum*, *Noviomagus*; examples of the additional elements include Gallo-Roman hybrids such as *Augustonemetum* and *Augustodunum*, both of which also exhibit the adaptation of the suffix form (originally *-on*) to Latin (*-um*), and such names as *Augusta Vindelicum* or *Aquae Granni*.

In Roman Britain, this way of adapting or taking over native toponyms was also clearly the rule. But places whose names in the Roman period are known are generally more important places, not the far more numerous villages and small settlements where the majority of people lived.¹⁹ Purely Latin names in Roman Britain are apparently very rare, and mixed Latin and Celtic names are not much more frequent; this situation is also reflected in other parts of the Empire such as Gaul or Germania. Toponyms of unknown or at least doubtful origin are problematic not only from an etymological point of view, but also from the point of view of assigning them to any particular language, language group, or ‘ethnic’ grouping. Since Latin toponyms could occur, however infrequently, it is entirely possible, given the right circumstances, that toponyms of some other origin—and foreign to the immediate region where they occur—could also appear.

Another point is the nature of the places involved. Settlements are one thing; but some toponyms are originally associated not with settlements, but with military installations. Such military installations may be of a permanent or temporary nature; temporary installations are much less likely to be named, of course. But occasionally temporary military installations may have been repurposed to permanent ones, especially in frontier areas. It may be remembered that Tacitus informs us that Agricola had *castella* built²⁰; in view of Tacitus’ claim that none of these was ever taken, it may be assumed that they were certainly not built *a priori* directly near settlements. What made good sense for military camps from a tactical point of view would have made even better sense for permanent bases²¹. One difference between temporary camps and permanent military bases may on occasion have involved their positioning. In some cases (e.g. the *castellum* at Rainau-Buch, Germany) the installation has clearly been made at a place permitting a very good view of the countryside round about. But sometimes a temporary camp was upgraded to become a more or less permanent base²².

19 Cf. Ross 2016:33: ‘Places with names known from the Roman period tend to be large and important military and civilian centres rather than the small villages and hamlets that much of the native population appeared to be living in.... This would suggest that “official” names, names that were recorded for official use, were only given to places that were important to the Romans. These sites are not small native settlements but towns, tribal *civitas* capitals and forts.’

20 Tacitus, Agr. 22 (2): *...nullum ab Agricola positum castellum aut vi hostium expugnatum aut pactione ac fuga desertum; nam adversus moras obsidionis annuis copiis firmabantur.*

21 See (on the topic of temporary installations) Welfare/Swan 1995:6-7: ‘The selection of a suitable site for a camp was a process that demanded some skill. Roman literary sources make it clear that this role fell to an advance party of surveyors ... ; they had to choose the best land available on the route and had to lay out an area corresponding to the size of the unit to be accommodated.... The texts make it clear, however, that ideally the camp should have been on a slight rise, with the main gate facing the enemy or the line of advance; the rear gate should have been set on the highest point, in order to provide an uninterrupted view over the surrounding countryside. Firewood, fodder and a good water-supply had to be readily available, and any risk of flooding had to be avoided. ... Although it was essentially a defensive structure, a camp ... was not seen as a place from which to fight but was the base from which a more active and mobile form of self-defence would be conducted. A dominant position ... was therefore not necessary. In most instances, nevertheless, great emphasis was evidently placed upon securing a position that had the benefit of some natural defence.’

22 Bishop 2012:17: ‘In at least one case, the defences of a temporary camp at Rhyn Park (Wales) appear to have been “hardened” to upgrade to winter-quarters standard, enhanced with added gateways and revetted ramparts.’

Owing mostly to the economic effect of the Roman military, civilian settlements could grow up around the permanent bases; this would appear to be the case in Vindolanda, for instance. At least, so far there has been no archaeological indication of a pre-Roman settlement there. This leads to the question of motivation for toponyms.

What is this place called?

‘A further hindrance to interpreting the names is the fact that many place-names ... do not owe their names to the actual circumstances of a place (e.g. the Nassauian place-names *Rauenthal*, *Reckental*, *Wirzentel* [now *Wirzenborn* near Montabaur] do not lie in a valley, but rather on a hill or slope); rather, they result from the effect of a fashion or have been transferred to a place which now bears them for some other reason ... , with the original sense of the name being quite unimportant. *Frankfurt* an der Oder is no “Ford of Franks” like its name-giving model on the Main. The village of *Haeselicht* in the Kulmer Land received its name after a member of the Silesian house of *Haeselicht*; thus, the literal meaning of the name, “hazel bush”, plays no role here at all. River names, too, can be transferred, even in ancient times, and their original sense may be lost entirely. Place-names in *-beek* [meaning “beck”] may occur where no stream ever flowed.’²³

With this (language-specific) situation in mind, it is worth recalling that, while the Romans did tend to use British Celtic names, i.e. the ‘autochthonous’ names in Roman eyes, this was not exclusively the case. The same is true of other areas in the Roman Empire. Newly-founded places could well end up with purely Latin names, even when Latin was far more the official language of government and administration rather than replacing the local idiom, which was actually true of much of the (early) Empire. Places such as *Legio* (modern León, capital of the Spanish region of the same name) or *Colonia Claudia Ara Agrippinensium* (modern Cologne in Germany)²⁴ show this.

On occasion, however, a place-name in some particular region occurs which is neither Latin nor native to the region in question; such names are e.g. Ἀντίπολις/*Antipolis* (modern Antibes, France) or Ἐμπορίον/*Emporion* (modern Empúries in Catalonia, Spain). Most frequently these are place-names in the Western Mediterranean of Greek origin, with a few being of Punic origin (such as, famously, Cartagena in Spain, which is Punic at least to a partial extent). It is true that these Mediterranean places were in existence—as were their names—before Roman rule; but there is no reason to suppose that foreigners of non-Roman origin might not have named places elsewhere during the Roman period. This will have been a rare occurrence, as most places surely already had names when the Romans arrived. But some few places were founded under Roman rule, for various reasons, so it is within the bounds of possibility to speculate that, should a particular place-name occur at a place that has no pre-Roman record of settlement archaeologically, this toponym could in fact have been given by someone other than the local population, and in some other than the local language, or even than Latin.

Just such a situation exists at Vindolanda, where so far no pre-Roman settlement has been found. This does not entirely exclude the possibility that a place-name may refer to something other than a settlement, but apart from the names of rivers or lakes and mountains or hills, there is not much evidence in ancient times for a locality simply being named after its appearance. This, however, is exactly what we are required to believe if the currently accepted etymology of the toponym Vindolanda is correct.

23 A. Bach, *Deutsche Namenkunde* II, 1, 247. My translation; the original reads: ‚Ein weiteres Hindernis für die Deutung der Namen ist die Tatsache, daß viele ON, wie schon erwähnt, nicht den sachlichen Gegebenheiten einer Örtlichkeit ihren Namen verdanken (die nassauischen ON *Rauenthal*, *Reckental*, *Wirzentel* [heute *Wirzenborn* b. Montabaur] z.B. liegen nicht im Tal, sondern auf einem Berg oder am Hang), vielmehr unter der Einwirkung einer Mode gegeben oder aus anderen Gründen auf den Ort übertragen worden sind ... , an dem sie heute haften, wobei der ursprüngliche Sinn des Namens nebensächlich war. *Frankfurt* a.d. Oder ist keine „Frankenfurt“ wie sein namengebendes Vorbild am Main. Das Dorf *Haeselicht* im Kulmer Land gewann seinen Namen nach einem Herrn aus dem schlesischen Geschlechte *Haeselicht*; hier kommt also die wörtliche Bedeutung des Namens „Haselgebüsch“ keineswegs in Frage. Auch Flußnamen können übertragen werden, auch in alter Zeit, und ihr ursprünglicher Sinn kann dabei gänzlich verloren gehen. ON auf *-beek* können auftreten, wo nie ein Bach geflossen ist.‘ [Italics and spacing according to the original.]

24 It is true that the settlement had been founded prior to being given this name; but it was nevertheless not an old settlement, and its elevation to the status of *colonia* in 50 AD resulted in a new name, which was entirely, rather than partially, Latin.

‘White Fields/Shining Fields/Bright Fields’ or similar is certainly not impossible; but there must be some kind of motivation for such a name, surely. It is highly unlikely that any old field or grassy area or whatever would have been given a specific name, unless the place had some kind of significance beyond its mere existence.²⁵ The possibility of a transfer of a toponym from some other locality as described by Bach (mentioned above, see FN 23) has the same limitation: a field or area without any further specificity would hardly be given a name even by transferral. All this having been said, it is worth remembering that ‘Ancient toponyms rarely convey fancy meanings; Celtic place-names, for example, usually describe the site in terms of its appearance or its outstanding feature. Investigators should therefore remember that the simplest meaning is most likely to be the correct one.’²⁶

One argument has been that many of the Roman army units sent to Britain were originally constituted (raised or conscripted) in presumably Celtic-dominated areas of NW Europe.²⁷

However, in at least one important case the units involved were anything but Celtic in nature. These were the Batavians, who we are told were Germanic.²⁸ Rome had a special treaty with them; they were valued as soldiers because of their skill in dealing with water, being apparently able to swim in full armour and on horseback too, as well as being excellent boatmen. Many of the Imperial bodyguards during the Julio-Claudian dynasty were Batavi, as witnessed by the epigraphical evidence²⁹. Even after their revolt (described by the Roman historian Tacitus in his *Histories*) they enjoyed special status, thus also under Domitian. They had taken part in the original Roman conquest of Britain under Claudius, and they are specifically mentioned by Tacitus not once, but twice in his biographical work *Agricola*.³⁰

The Batavi were auxiliaries, numbering a total of at least eight cohorts (at least in AD 43 in Britain, and mentioned again in the year 61, if we can trust Dio Cassius and Tacitus). The Ninth Cohort of Batavi (*cohors viiii batavorum*) and the Third Cohort of Tungri were both at Vindolanda, albeit at varying times, in the late 1st and early 2nd centuries AD. This rather disposes of the argument that most Roman soldiers (or even necessarily a majority of them) in Britain came from Celtic-speaking areas and therefore ‘many of them would have been very comfortable with the native language’ (Ross 2011:35).³¹ Doubtless there were some soldiers who were; but it seems probable that Latin would have been the preferred language, something we may also infer at Vindolanda.³² This is particularly so in view of the distinct probability that there were Germanic soldiers in not inconsiderable numbers; after all, Tungria and Batavia were most certainly not areas of Celtic speech.

Also, some soldiers in any given unit of the Roman army came from very different places throughout the Empire, some from the general area of the Eastern Mediterranean, some from the general area of North Africa, and some from other parts of Central or Southern Europe. This would have rendered it nearly impossible not to use Latin for most or all communication within the units, and the evidence suggests that this was the usual situation.³³

Naturally the use of languages other than Latin is not excluded, but the number of Roman soldiers who were ‘comfortable with the native language’ would not have been great. Apart from that, the ‘Roman’ view of the ‘natives’ was anything but complimentary, if we can judge by Tab. Vind. II 164³⁴, so that it seems unlikely that the native language of the area would have enjoyed any

25 There has been some discussion of the toponomastic element *vindo-*, with doubt being cast on the interpretation as ‘white’ or ‘bright’. Cf. i.a. Durham, A. (2021). *Vindo-* in Early Place Names. *Academia Letters*, Article 4033. <https://doi.org/10.20935/AL4033>.

26 Curchin 1997:2.

27 Ross 2011:35 writes: ‘Mattingly notes that overall, “there appears to have been a strong preference for sending to Britain units originally raised through mass conscription in what we may term the ‘Celtic’ sphere—Germany (over 30), Gaul (25) or Spain (10).” ’ FN 387 gives ‘Mattingly, D. (2006) p. 168’. This reference is to D. Mattingly, *An Imperial Possession: Britain in the Roman Empire, 54BC - AD409*. Allen Lane, London 2006 [*non vidit*].

28 See also Fear 2011 on the Batavians and Vindolanda.

29 Fear op.cit. 68.

30 Tac. *Agricola* 18 and 36.

31 Meaning the Celtic language(s) of Britain at that time.

32 See also Bowman 1994: 82-99 on the topic of literacy.

33 But one must bear in mind Speidel’s cogent warning (Speidel 2023:142): ‘Although the evidence strongly suggests that in each centuria of about eighty men there were at least some common soldiers who could read and write Latin, it is, again, surely advisable to remain cautious when drawing general conclusions merely from the number of the surviving tablets with regard to the Latin skills of Vindolanda’s military community at large.’

34 See e.g. Bowman 1994:106.

kind of prestige, at least during the conquest and the first few decades thereafter. If anyone among the Roman military spoke it (or Gaulish, which was probably similar), then likely only in cases of necessary and unavoidable communication between the 'Roman' and 'native' sides.³⁵ In any case, the question of Celtic language probably does not enter at all at the moment of conquest of Northern Britain under Agricola.

While this by no means excludes the use of a native toponym, it does increase the possibility that this might be a case where a foreign toponym was applied. It is entirely possible that the toponym is Germanic, if the fort at Vindolanda was indeed founded by a cohort of Batavians or Tungrians. Certainly it is odd that the toponomastic element *vindo-* is fairly frequent along Hadrian's Wall and its environs, but that no other place-name known to us in that region contains the element *landa-*. This, of course, fits in with the noticeable rarity of this element elsewhere in the Roman world.

A most significant factor in the case of a Batavian cohort being the founders of the fort at Vindolanda is the fact that these auxiliaries were not only soldiers in the Roman army, but served in the same unit with their native nobles as commanders.³⁶ This might well have favoured the use of Germanic in giving a newly-founded fort a name. Another possibility is that the *canaba* or *vicus*, either or both of which will have soon come into being³⁷, was given the name, rather than the fort itself.

However this may have been exactly, the likelihood that the name *Vindolanda* is Celtic is clearly reduced.

Other Possibilities: Celtic After All?

Let us assume that the toponomastic element **land(a)* was present in early Celtic languages. Even as a loanword from Germanic, this might be possible. It would, however, have to have been a very early loan. Whether as a loanword or inherited, we would then expect at least some distribution in what is known to us as Celtic-speaking territory. What we have is extremely close to no distribution or occurrence at all.

So what is going on? Is this simply a very, very rare toponomastic element in Celtic? That is hardly a likely case. Looking at another, semantically similar toponomastic element in Ancient Celtic, *-magos*, it can be seen that this element is found very frequently indeed. There seems a very strong case, then, for **-land(a)* being not only unusual, but originally actually absent in the Celtic toponomastic vocabulary.

Conclusion

In the end, there can be no certainty without some kind of confirmation or refutation either through further archaeological discovery or by epigraphical means. But taking the place-names as our guide, it would seem at the least very strongly advisable not to place too much trust in the Celtic interpretation of the element **-land(a)*. It is surely far better to voice an honest doubt than to propagate a false certainty.

35 This is referring to the short period of the actual conquest of the region. There may nonetheless have been 'interpreters', as there had been some 40 years' time at this point for people to either learn the language(s) of Britain, or at the very least for native Britons to have joined the army. But the entire question is difficult; an important contribution in this regard is Mairs 2020.

36 See i.a. Roymans 2004:223. Speidel 2023:144 writes: 'Particularly during the first century or so of the imperial army's existence, many *alae* and *cohortes* were commanded by members from the aristocracy of those tribes from which these units were formed.' (See his FN 55 for his sources.) But this may actually refer primarily - or only - to the Batavian units.

37 See Tomas 2017:14ff. and Sommer 2006:97ff. and 107-108 for further information on the matter of *canabae* and *vici*.

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